

ETCOR

INTERNATIONAL
MULTIDISCIPLINARY
RESEARCH CONFERENCE

Educational Research Center Inc.
SEC Reg. No. 2024020137294-00

Sta. Ana, Pampanga, Philippines

Website: <https://etcor.org>

iJOINED ETCOR
P - ISSN 2984-7567
E - ISSN 2945-3577

The Exigency
P - ISSN 2984-7842
E - ISSN 1908-3181

Teacher Competence Towards Job Satisfaction and Teachers' Performance in Region 10: Basis for Teachers' Leadership Development Plan

Dr. Luzviminda B. Ragmac¹, Dr. Chibert L. Jala^{2*}

^{1,2} Lumbia National High School, Department of Education, Region 10

Corresponding Author email: cjala@liceo.edu.ph

Received: 11 October 2024

Revised: 14 November 2024

Accepted: 16 November 2024

Available Online: 16 November 2024

Volume III (2024), Issue 4, P-ISSN – 2984-7567; E-ISSN - 2945-3577

Abstract

Aim: This research aimed to determine the teaching competence towards job satisfaction and teacher performance of secondary school teachers of Cagayan de Oro City and Misamis Oriental for the School Year 2020-2021.

Methodology: This study utilized a descriptive-survey method of research, a patterned and modified questionnaire of Javillonar and Boni of 2023. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation to describe the variables of the study where the three hundred fifty secondary (350) secondary public school teachers from the two divisions of Cagayan de Oro City are the respondents of the study.

Results: The study examined with a 0.01 correlation coefficient (two-tailed) on the significance between teacher competence, job satisfaction, and job performance found that teachers demonstrated high competence in critical thinking, teamwork, leadership, professionalism, and career management. The job satisfaction was generally high, but areas like compensation, facilities, and interpersonal relationships showed lower satisfaction. Teachers also demonstrated high performance in content, pedagogy, diversity of learners, curriculum planning, and community linkage. It has found out that there is a significant positive correlation between teacher competence and job satisfaction and performance, suggesting that teachers with strong competence are more likely to experience higher job satisfaction and superior performance.

Conclusion: The teacher's proficiency in influencing job satisfaction and performance outcomes demonstrated high competence in essential skills; concerns in areas like compensation and interpersonal relationships impact overall satisfaction levels. The positive correlation between teacher competence, job satisfaction, and performance underscores the need for investing in professional development to enhance skills and engagement. Their skill is crucial in creating job satisfaction, which means an improvement in teaching skills is correlated with higher job satisfaction levels.

Keywords: teachers' competence, job satisfaction, and teachers' performance

INTRODUCTION

Teacher competence, job satisfaction, and teachers' performance are having strong connections. Competent teachers who are satisfied with their jobs tend to perform better and contribute more effectively to student learning and school success. This paper explores the relationship between these important factors in the education field. It examines how teacher competence, defined as the knowledge, skills, and abilities necessary for effective teaching, can influence job satisfaction and, in turn, impact teacher performance in the classroom. The findings shed light on strategies to enhance teacher competence, job satisfaction, and ultimately, the quality of education provided to students.

Education is one of the key components in nation-building. Its primary goal of this department is to produce people who are capable of addressing the issues associated with growth in a given nation. When hiring teachers, it is assumed that they would go above and beyond to help their pupils catch up. This necessitates that their instructors and the company they work for be satisfied with their job. Educators who were very satisfied with their jobs devoted more time, energy, and effort to increasing output. This increased dedication ultimately benefits the students, as they

346

ETCOR

INTERNATIONAL
MULTIDISCIPLINARY
RESEARCH CONFERENCE

Educational Research Center Inc.
SEC Reg. No. 2024020137294-00

Sta. Ana, Pampanga, Philippines

Website: <https://etcor.org>

iJOINED ETCOR
P - ISSN 2984-7567
E - ISSN 2945-3577

The Exigency
P - ISSN 2984-7842
E - ISSN 1908-3181

receive a higher-quality education. Therefore, ensuring teacher satisfaction is crucial for the success of the education system as a whole.

Competence is one of the important characteristics of a teacher. A teacher cannot teach and perform his job, given that he does not fully equip himself with the domains that are stipulated in DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017, the National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST). Teachers are important components in nation-building and acquiring a better future. Quality teachers will help the Philippines develop holistic learners who are quite steeped in values, equipped with 21st-century skills, and can propel this country forward toward development and progress. This aligns with the vision set by the Department of Education through DepEd Order No. 36, s. 2013: The department of education's vision, mission, and core values in developing "Filipinos who passionately love their country and whose values and competencies enable them to realize their full potential and contribute meaningfully to building the nation." Konig et al. (2020) cited that competent teachers are essential for ensuring high-quality instruction and promoting student achievement in context-specific cognitive performance dispositions that are functionally responsive to situations and demands in certain domains. Pedagogical competence, personal competence, social competence, and professional competence are identified as key components of teacher competence. These components encompass a teacher's ability to effectively plan and deliver lessons, manage classroom dynamics, build positive relationships with students, and continuously improve their teaching practices. By possessing these competencies, teachers can create a supportive learning environment that enhances student learning outcomes.

On the other hand, job satisfaction within the work environment is one of the issues confronting our teachers in public schools. Others would claim that job satisfaction is achieved when it is really one's passion to demonstrate and implement a job well, while others would conform that salaries and fringe benefits play vital roles in achieving job satisfaction. The Department of Education has already exerted its effort to increase the salary of teachers and provide them with personal services funds to sustain their basic needs and priorities, such as Personnel Economic Relief Allowance (PERA), which is given monthly as stated in DepEd Order No. 77, s. 1991, Clothing/Uniform Allowance, which is given yearly, Mid-Year and Year-End bonuses, which are equivalent to 13th-month and 14th-month salaries, Special hardship allowance, World-teacher's Day incentives, and Step-increment due to teachers after every three years of service. Although they have been receiving all these, there are still clamors and protests to increase their salaries for reasons that these benefits and salaries are not enough to motivate them fully to deliver their craft effectively.

The teacher competence has the ability to guide and support student learning in a way that is both engaging and impactful. Teachers need a deep understanding of their subject matter as well as the different ways students learn. They need to know how to break down complex ideas into manageable chunks and how to connect learning to real-world experience. Pedagogical competence, personal competence, social competence, and professional competence are identified as key components of teacher competence. These competences determine how well teachers fulfill their roles as educators, including their preparedness, their ability to handle responsibilities, and the effectiveness of their teaching practices. When teachers possess these core competences, they are more likely to experience job satisfaction, which in turn positively influences their performance in the classroom. (Sides & Cuevas, 2020)

This study, on the other hand, investigated the competence of teachers and their relationship to job satisfaction in the two divisions of Misamis Oriental and Cagayan de Oro City. Further, this study determined the relationship between the teachers' level of job satisfaction and their job performance through their performance ratings, using the uniform key result areas from the RPMS Tools for Teachers and the Department of Education's Order No. 2, s. 2015.

It is anchored on DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017, which is the National Adaptation and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST). It recognizes the importance of teachers' competence in continuing professional development and teachers based on lifelong learning.

Also, Herzberg's Motivation Theory suggests that job satisfaction and dissatisfaction are two opposite ends of the same continuum but are also separate and, at times, even concepts. To determine the level of competence of teachers based on leadership, professionalism/work ethic, teamwork, collaboration, critical thinking, problem solving, career management, and levels of job satisfaction based on perks, working conditions, schools' facilities, and interpersonal relationships. Similarly, motivating factors like pay and benefits, recognition, and achievement need to be met in order for an employee to be satisfied with work.

ETCOR Educational Research Center Inc.
SEC Reg. No. 2024020137294-00

Sta. Ana, Pampanga, Philippines

INTERNATIONAL
MULTIDISCIPLINARY
RESEARCH CONFERENCE

Website: <https://etcor.org>

iJOINED ETCOR
P - ISSN 2984-7567
E - ISSN 2945-3577

The Exigency
P - ISSN 2984-7842
E - ISSN 1908-3181

Furthermore, the nature and expectations of the job have a positive impact on employees' job satisfaction and performance. Demir (2020) cited that job satisfaction reflects how employees feel and think about their work. Professional development opportunities are available and, occasionally, new positions are created to ensure that unique talents are brought to the company. From the viewpoint of the employee who is doing well, they have an increased ability to understand what the most critical requirements are for fulfilling a job and grasp how much it covers in terms of operational areas as well as knowledge and skills needed. And businesses and organizations will get the best services possible. Employees are paid to work and it is a natural foundation for an effective workforce.

Research has repeatedly shown that teachers' work satisfaction plays a critical role in increasing their efficacy and, as a result, boosting student results. Good connections with coworkers and students, opportunity for professional growth, and moderate workloads are all factors that positively impact teachers' job satisfaction. Furthermore, a happy workplace can result in higher rates of teacher retention and general academic performance. (Banerjee et al., 2017).

The school environment and its impact on teaching competencies is the extent to which the school organization has been able to achieve the stated goals and objectives and how well its performance in the process. Effectiveness is one of the performance groups of the educational system that needs to be given priority in light of the interdependence among educational inputs, processes, and outputs. It is essential for teachers to continually assess and improve their teaching competencies in order to enhance the overall effectiveness of the school environment. This can lead to better student outcomes and a more job satisfaction experience for all involved (Mulyani et al., 2020).

Objectives

This study determined the relationship between the teachers' level of job satisfaction and their job performance from the division of Misamis Oriental and Cagayan de Oro City.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the respondents' level of teaching competence based on:
 - a. Critical Thinking/Problem Solving;
 - b. Teamwork and collaboration
 - c. Leadership;
 - d. Professionalism/Work Ethics; and
 - e. Career Management?
2. What is the respondents' level of job satisfaction considering the following:
 - a. Compensation and Fringe Benefits;
 - b. Working Condition;
 - c. School Facilities
 - d. Interpersonal Relationship; and
 - e. Motivation?
3. What is the teachers' performance in terms of:
 - a. Content and Pedagogy;
 - b. Diversity of Learners;
 - c. Curriculum and Planning; and
 - d. Community Linkages?
4. To what extent does a teacher's competence significantly contribute to their job satisfaction?
5. To what extent does a teacher's competence significantly contribute to their job performance?
6. An in-depth interview among teachers on their personal views on what are their motivation to continue working in their current positions?

Hypothesis

Given the stated research problem, the following hypotheses were:

Problems 1, 2, and 3 are hypotheses-free. On the basis of Problems 4 and 5, the following null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance.

H01: The teacher's competence does not contribute significantly to job satisfaction.

H02: The teacher's competence does not contribute significantly to job performance.

ETCOR

INTERNATIONAL
MULTIDISCIPLINARY
RESEARCH CONFERENCE

Educational Research Center Inc.
SEC Reg. No. 2024020137294-00

Sta. Ana, Pampanga, Philippines

Website: <https://etcor.org>

iJOINED ETCOR
P - ISSN 2984-7567
E - ISSN 2945-3577

The Exigency
P - ISSN 2984-7842
E - ISSN 1908-3181

METHODS

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-survey method of research that utilized a survey questionnaire to gather the necessary data.

Population and Sampling

The respondents of the study were the three hundred fifty(350) secondary school teachers of Cagayan de Oro City and secondary school teachers of Misamis Oriental Division. The computation of the sample size was based on the total number of secondary school teachers in the division of Cagayan de Oro City and the Misamis Oriental division. The researchers used Slovin's formula with 5% margin of error in determining the desired sample size.

Instrument

This study used the patterned and modified survey questionnaire from the study of Javillonar and Boni (2023). It was run through a series of validations by the expert in the field and was used in gathering the data.

Data Collection

Data collection was conducted using a manuscript presentation and a written consent form outlining the study's purpose and objectives. After receiving the approved letter from the department with its consent form and a letter explaining the study's purpose, rationale, and objectives were sent to the respondents. It assures that the study adhered to proper protocols on Data Privacy Act, ensuring the security and confidentiality of all information. Participants were informed of their rights and given the option to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences.

Treatment of Data

The analysis and interpretation of data were facilitated through the use of the following statistical tools:

1. Descriptive statistics such as mean; standard deviation were employed to describe the variables in the study.
2. Pearson r Analysis was employed to determine the significant relationship between teaching competence toward job satisfaction and teachers' performance.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers ensured that all research protocols involving ethics in research were complied with for the protection of all people and institutions involved in the conduct of the study by complying with all the guidelines and adherence to R.A 10173.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

The data gathered further discuss the teacher respondents' competence towards job satisfaction and job performance of secondary teachers in Cagayan de Oro and Misamis Oriental.

The respondents' level of competence based on Critical Thinking/Problem Solving, Teamwork and Collaboration; Leadership; Professionalism/Work Ethics; and Career Management

A competent teacher supports the curriculum's process and is well-versed in the areas it teaches. She is eager to investigate and develop novel teaching strategies that are appropriate for the students' learning style and pace. In addition to making judgments, the astute and capable instructor tries to get to know her pupils. She approaches everything with thought and analysis. Additionally, critical thinking/problem solving, professionalism/work ethics, cooperation and collaboration, and leadership are crucial measures of a teacher's competency that should be taken into consideration while evaluating and supporting their professional growth.

Critical thinking/Problem-solving is self-belief, and lifelong learning was found to have no significant relationship with reflective thinking. Table 1 presents the distribution of Respondents' Level of Competence in terms of Critical Thinking and Problem Solving.

Table 1. Distribution of the Respondents' Level of Teaching Competence in term of;

Indicator	Mean	SD	Description
A. Critical Thinking/Problem Solving	3.49	0.455	At All times
B. Teamwork and Collaboration	3.52	0.399	At All times
C. Leadership	3.40	0.369	At All times
D. Professionalism/Work Ethics	3.52	0.399	At All times
E. Career Management	3.42	0.481	At All times
Overall total	3.47	.4208	At All Times

Legend: 3.26-4.00 At all Times 1.76-2.50 Sometimes
 2.51-3.25 Most of the time 1.00-1.75 Never

Table 1 shows the respondent's level of teaching competence with an **overall mean of 3.47 (SD= 4108)**, described as **"At all times"**. This implies that the teacher respondents are competent and, therefore, qualified teachers in the field. A teacher actively promotes learning and holds the belief that every student is capable of learning. It also underscores the idea that learning extends beyond the traditional confines of the classroom, indicating that education can happen in various settings and contexts. To this end, the teacher takes every opportunity to improve on his own professional practice in order to provide quality learning. Good teaching does not occur in a vacuum (Dagoc, 2021).

It can be noted from the table that **"Teamwork and Collaboration,"** obtained the **highest mean** of 3.52 (SD= 0.399), described as **At All Times**. This implies that the teachers are considered competent if they can win the hearts and minds of the students , gaining their respect and trust through effective communication and engaging teaching methods. Ultimately, a competent teacher is one who can inspire and motivate students to reach their full potential (Rodriguez, 2020). This means that teamwork and collaboration are observed at all times by the teachers, that the teachers demonstrate a very high level of teaching competence and display a wide range of delegating responsibilities and promote a sense of trust in the school environment. It can be gleaned from school activity that teachers' tasks were completed. As well as the conviction is observed of teachers to work as a group (Seryal et. al 2020). Collaboration with the groups indicate that the general level of school support for teamwork is evidently modest and positively correlated. The purpose of school support is to help interprofessional school staff members work better together as a team and to enhance their ability to behave in an interprofessional manner.

On the other hand, **" Professionalism and Work Ethics"** has equal mean value with **"teamwork and collaboration"** with the mean of 3.52 (SD= 0.399), described **At all times**. This implies that the teacher-responders are not only skilled in their area of specialization, but also highly professional and have incorporated work ethics into their daily routine. Teachers are the most qualified professionals in their industry in addition to being skilled in their chosen field. This conforms to the study of Rodriguez (2021) that teacher-respondents keep a professional demeanor, make concessions, and answer quickly to the demands of the organization. Two crucial components are work ethics and professionalism. Teachers never forgot or failed to remember that an effective teacher needed to be professional and have strong morals, abilities, and knowledge.

This also means that teachers demonstrate respect for co-teachers, uphold professionalism, and uphold work ethics within their organization, ensuring high ethical standards and harmonious relationships within the organization. Likewise, professional ethics is like a guide, facilitating the teacher to provide quality education and inculcate good values among learners. As observed, teachers in secondary school must be a good model with good values and

ETCOR Educational Research Center Inc.
SEC Reg. No. 2024020137294-00

Sta. Ana, Pampanga, Philippines

INTERNATIONAL
MULTIDISCIPLINARY
RESEARCH CONFERENCE

Website: <https://etcor.org>

iJOINED ETCOR
P - ISSN 2984-7567
E - ISSN 2945-3577

The Exigency
P - ISSN 2984-7842
E - ISSN 1908-3181

attitudes worth emulating for young adolescent learners. Gusman (2017) expounds to teachers on the significance of upholding these ethics because of their profession.

Lastly, the indicator "leadership" obtained the lowest mean of 3.40 (SD = 0.369), described as At All Times. This implies that although teacher-respondents are competent in their field as teachers and very professional in their ways, they are not so good when it comes to leadership. The leadership competence of the respondents was not low, apart from the fact that they have applied leadership in their respective schools. Teacher leadership is crucial to increasing students' learning and achievement. Leadership will not only take place within the four walls but instead even in a larger community. This implies that teachers are competent, and thus, teachers apply leadership in school, and teacher leadership is crucial to the achievement of the mission and vision of the school. Thus, school leaders empower teachers to exercise their leadership potential, requiring them to enhance their leadership skills to achieve school organization goals and objectives. (Paiton, 2017).

Teachers are now able to utilize their leadership potential, as you have seen, especially with the authority that has been bestowed upon them by school administrators. In order to achieve the aims and objectives of the school organization, teachers themselves must develop their leadership abilities (Rodriguez, 2021).

The respondents' level of Job satisfaction considering the Compensation and Fringe Benefits; Working Condition; School Facilities; Interpersonal Relationships, and Motivation

Job satisfaction plays an essential role in the overall commitment and productivity of the school organization. The teachers' job satisfaction significantly influenced their commitment to the organization. Teachers who are satisfied with the job are also committed to working in the organization. The more the employers are satisfied with the job, the better is their participation and commitment to the organization. The happy or satisfied feeling of the teachers towards the organization affects the overall process of carrying out their job, thus contributing to the school's success as a whole (Baluyos et al., 2019).

Table 2. Distribution of the Respondents' Level of Job Satisfaction

Indicator	Mean	SD	Description
a. Compensation and Fringe Benefits	3.05	0.544	Most of the Time
b. Working Condition	3.27	0.492	At All times
c. School Facilities	2.84	0.899	At All times
d. Interpersonal Relationship	3.00	0.316	Most of the Time
e. Motivation	3.34	0.46	At All times
Overall total	3.10	.5422	Most of the Time

Legend: 3.26-4.00 At all Times 1.76-2.50 Sometimes
2.51-3.25 Most of the time 1.00-1.75 Never

Table 2 shows the respondent's level of teaching competence with an **overall mean of 3.10 (SD= .5422)**, described as "**Most of the time**". Focusing on teachers' job satisfaction implies as one essential for retaining high-quality educators in schools. Giving priority and enhancement programs towards job satisfaction as a considered prime key competency that schools can create a positive work environment. It also means that this is vital support towards teachers' competencies. It is not only boosts teacher retention rates but also positively impacts students' academic performance and well-being. With job satisfaction, it fosters a stable and supportive learning environment, leading to an improved school environment.

It emphasizes that teachers have a significant role in the quality of education related to job satisfaction. Job satisfaction is an important factor in employee retention and recruitment. The satisfaction of teachers is crucial for their overall well-being and performance, which directly impacts student learning and achievement (Kadtong et al., 2017).

ETCOR Educational Research Center Inc.
SEC Reg. No. 2024020137294-00

Sta. Ana, Pampanga, Philippines

INTERNATIONAL
MULTIDISCIPLINARY
RESEARCH CONFERENCE

Website: <https://etcor.org>

iJOINED ETCOR
P - ISSN 2984-7567
E - ISSN 2945-3577

The Exigency
P - ISSN 2984-7842
E - ISSN 1908-3181

Relatively, the sense of pleasure and satisfaction teachers get from their profession is known as teacher job satisfaction. It highlights two important factors: professional satisfaction, which reflects happiness with the choice to pursue a career in teaching, and satisfaction with the school environment, which indicates enjoyment and desire to promote the school as a wonderful workplace. By emphasizing these elements, it validates that teacher satisfaction is holistic in terms of both work environment and career choice (Olsen & Huang, 2019).

It also showed that the respondents' level of job satisfaction in terms of motivation expectations had the highest identified mean value, with 3.34 (SD = 0.460) described as "All the Times." It connotes that teachers were motivated to make a conscious effort to give their best in order to complete the work of their own accord. This dedication often resulted in high-quality lessons and a positive learning environment for students. According to Arevalo (2020), motivation is necessary for both individuals and organizations to accomplish goals and objectives, whether they work alone or in teams.

This also means that teachers-respondents are passionate about their jobs and students, dedicated to providing high-quality education and fostering a positive learning environment, leading to better academic achievement and personal growth. This is true since motivation is the willingness of an employee to contribute high levels of effort toward his or her work.

However, Table 2 displays the respondents' level of job satisfaction in terms of school facilities and presents the lowest mean rating of 2.84 (SD = 0.899), described as Most of the Time. It means that most of the time, the respondents observed job satisfaction in terms of the use of facilities in their school. Results imply that they need adequate school facilities for teaching and learning. Although the school administrator monitors the physical condition of the school, considering a lot of potential improvements on its available resources that could be attained, there is still a lack of school facilities and a need to be addressed. This demonstrated that several schools within the division do not have the necessary facilities, which both instructors and students find challenging to get.

The respondents' level of teachers' performance in terms of Knowledge and Pedagogy; the Diversity of Learners; the Curriculum and Planning; and the Community Linkages

In line with the new professional standards for teachers, the Department of Education (DepEd), through the Teacher Education Council (TEC), issued a DepEd order entitled National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST).

DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017 emphasizes the importance of professional standards in teacher development and lifelong learning, recognizing the crucial role of good teachers in student achievement and long-term nation-building. Quality teachers develop holistic learners with values and 21st-century skills, propelling the Philippines towards development and progress.

Table 3. Distribution of the Respondents' Level of Performance in term of;

Indicator	Mean	SD	Description
f. Content and Pedagogy	4.56	0.508	Outstanding
g. Diversity of Learners	4.49	0.539	Very Satisfactory
h. Curriculum and Planning	4.42	0.544	Very Satisfactory
i. Community Linkages	4.44	0.647	Very Satisfactory
Overall total	4.48	.559	Very Satisfactory

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Outstanding 2.50-3.49 Satisfactory
3.50-4.49 Most of the time 1.00-2.49 Unsatisfactory

Table 3 presents the respondents level of performance with an overall result of 4.48 (SD = .559) described as very satisfactory performance. The respondents' evaluation of teachers' performance across various domains such as content and pedagogy, diversity of learners, curriculum and planning, and community linkages yielded a remarkable

ETCOR

INTERNATIONAL
MULTIDISCIPLINARY
RESEARCH CONFERENCE

Educational Research Center Inc.
SEC Reg. No. 2024020137294-00

Sta. Ana, Pampanga, Philippines

Website: <https://etcor.org>

iJOINED ETCOR
P - ISSN 2984-7567
E - ISSN 2945-3577

The Exigency
P - ISSN 2984-7842
E - ISSN 1908-3181

general mean average score, indicating a very satisfactory level of performance that signifies teachers' not only met but exceeded expectations, surpassing the established standards for all goals, objectives, and targets. The results reflect an outstanding level of competence and effectiveness in teaching practices, curriculum development, classroom management, and community engagement, showcasing a high level of professionalism and dedication among the educators. These results demonstrate the commitment of the teachers to providing quality education and fostering strong relationships within the community. The high level of performance across all areas highlights the positive impact that effective teaching practices and collaboration with various stakeholders can have on student learning outcomes.

Taryana et al. (2023) state that understanding the complexities of education and being able to comprehend and communicate the numerous types of knowledge that must be learned throughout a certain school period are characteristics of a professional teacher. The career of a teacher is extremely different from that of an average employee, who just performs his duties in compliance with the laws, his profession, and the scientific discipline he possesses. Since they have a strong relationship with the students who will shape the future of the country and state, teachers have unique obligations regarding the sustainability of a nation and state. Thus, it can be said that the quality of national education in a developed nation has a significant impact on that nation and that teachers play a major role in determining the quality of national education.

Competence is the ability of the individual to perform tasks. The concept of competence is also interpreted as knowledge, skills, and professional identity that is certainly going to affect performance.

The respondents' level of competence in terms of **Content and Pedagogy** obtained the highest mean value with an overall mean of **4.56 (SD=0.508)**, described as Outstanding. The respondents' performance in their schools indicates that teachers are proficient in Key Outcome Areas, apply KRA indicators, and are subject matter experts. Their positive performance may indicate a strong support system, fostering a conducive learning environment, indicating the overall effectiveness of the educational system. The respondents' performance in their schools indicates that teachers are proficient in Key Outcome Areas, apply KRA indicators, and are subject matter experts. Their positive performance may indicate a strong support system, fostering a conducive learning environment and indicating the overall effectiveness of the educational system. This indicates that performance is a remarkable degree of accomplishment and dedication in terms of time, quality, technical expertise, and knowledge. Aside from job expertise in every aspect of the assigned role, this is dependent on the talents displayed and done. Thus, this performance of teachers reflects the dedication and expertise they bring to their roles, impacting the success of students and the overall reputation of the educational institution. The consistent demonstration of high performance is essential for ensuring continued growth and success in the academic setting.

However, the presented level of competence in terms of curriculum and planning showed the lowest mean value of 4.42 (SD = 0.544), described as very satisfactory. This describes how active teacher engagement in curriculum planning and development is essential for fostering a robust and effective educational system. By involving teachers in the process of shaping the curriculum across all subjects and specializations, empower them to become experts in their respective fields. This collaborative approach not only enhances the quality of instruction but also fosters a sense of ownership and commitment among teachers, leading to a more dynamic and responsive learning environment. The development of the curriculum is crucial for the implementation plan, involving committees in proposal initiation, data gathering, investigations, parent contact, note-taking, and curriculum creation.

ETCOR Educational Research Center Inc.
SEC Reg. No. 2024020137294-00

Sta. Ana, Pampanga, Philippines

INTERNATIONAL
MULTIDISCIPLINARY
RESEARCH CONFERENCE

Website: <https://etcor.org>

iJOINED ETCOR
P - ISSN 2984-7567
E - ISSN 2945-3577

The Exigency
P - ISSN 2984-7842
E - ISSN 1908-3181

The extent of a teacher's competence that significantly contributes to their job satisfaction.

Teachers' competence is their ability to perform or carry out defined tasks in a particular context at a high level of excellence and how they feel about a particular context at a high level of excellence, and how they feel about their job is the extent to which they dislike.

Table 4 the Pearson R-values showing the relationship between Teachers Competence and Job Satisfaction

Teaching Competence	Job Satisfaction										Description
	Compensation and Fringe Benefits		Working Condition		School Facilities		Interpersonal Relationship		Motivation		
	r	p	r	p	r	p	r	p	r	p	
Critical thinking/ Problem Solving	.184*	.001	.221*	.000	.245*	.000	.196*	.000	.271*	.000	Significant
Teamwork/Collaboration	.235*	.000	.233*	.000	.285*	.000	.225*	.000	.339*	.000	Significant
Leadership	0.047	.380	.139*	.009	0.06	.303	-0.014	0.798	.137*	.010	not significant
Professionalism/Work Ethics	.235*	.000	.233*	.000	.285*	.000	.225*	.000	.339*	.000	Significant
Career Management	.237*	.000	.312*	.000	.270*	.000	.202*	.000	.327*	.000	Significant

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level

Table 4 discloses that there is a significant relationship between teaching competence and job satisfaction with critical thinking/problem-solving. Teamwork/collaboration, professionalism/work ethics, and career management are positively given $r = 0.169$, which is statistically significant at $(P) 0.000$. Thus the null hypothesis is rejected. The positive work environments are closely associated with teacher satisfaction. Teachers' total job happiness is greatly influenced by elements such as competitive benefits, comfortable working circumstances, well-equipped facilities, and strong connections with coworkers. Additionally, teachers who work in a favorable environment are more motivated and productive. Teachers are more likely to be involved in their profession and dedicated to the achievement of their pupils when they feel appreciated and supported at work. Overall, creating a positive work environment for teachers can lead to higher job satisfaction and increased effectiveness in the classroom. It is essential for school administrators to prioritize the well-being of their staff in order to foster a successful learning environment for students. Dagoc (2021), states that the more the teachers are happy with their job, the more they perform well in their job and are able to positively impact their students' learning and development. Ultimately, creating a positive work environment for teachers can lead to improved outcomes for students.

ETCOR Educational Research Center Inc.
SEC Reg. No. 2024020137294-00

Sta. Ana, Pampanga, Philippines

INTERNATIONAL
MULTIDISCIPLINARY
RESEARCH CONFERENCE

Website: <https://etcor.org>

iJOINED ETCOR
P - ISSN 2984-7567
E - ISSN 2945-3577

The Exigency
P - ISSN 2984-7842
E - ISSN 1908-3181

To what extent does teaching competence significantly contribute to their teachers’ performance?

Teachers’ competence is their ability to perform or carry out defined tasks in a particular context at a high level of excellence and how their result is measured by the job given by their superior using the Result-based Performance Management System (RPMS) tool of the Department of Education.

Table 5. Pearson R-Values showing Relationship between Teacher’s Competence and Teachers’ Performance

Teaching Competence	Variable	Mean	Pearson R-value	p	Description
	Job Satisfaction	3.51	0.406	.000	Significant
	Teaching Performance	4.48	0.672	.000	Significant

***Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (two-tailed)*

The table discloses that there is a significant relationship between teachers’ competence and job performance, which are both statistically significant at (P) 0.000. Thus the null hypothesis is rejected.

On the other hand, the same table shows that teaching competence is found to be positively correlated with job satisfaction (r = 0.406). It further implies that as teachers are competent in their field, their job satisfaction and engagement in work tend to increase. This means that giving importance to improving teachers' competence can lead to higher job satisfaction and performance outcomes. Therefore, organizations should focus on providing professional development opportunities to enhance teachers' skills and knowledge; this will ultimately benefit both the teachers and the organization as a whole. By investing in training and development programs, schools can create a more positive and productive work environment for their educators, leading to improved student outcomes and overall success. Kim (2019) highlights that teachers’ competence in teaching pertains to the level of satisfaction and performance towards their workplace. It is essential for teachers to continuously update their knowledge and skills to effectively engage students and create a positive learning environment. Related to the study of Dagoc (2021) also confirmed that the higher the level of teachers’ competence, the more satisfied they are with their job. It implies that when teachers are satisfied with their work, then they could lead to better job performance and competence in the different aspects of being a teacher.

Furthermore, the same table reveals that teachers’ performance is positively related to teachers’ competence (r 672). It implies that both variables are dependent on each other in such a way that as recognized, job satisfaction and teachers’ performance also do improve. Paiton (2017): The perceived organizational support has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction and organizational commitments, leading to higher levels of teacher engagement and retention. This highlights the importance of fostering a supportive work environment to enhance overall organizational performance.

An in-depth interview among teachers on their personal views on what are their motivation to continue working in their current position

The positive results of the current study on teachers’ competence in job performance and job satisfaction were validated using in-depth interviews among the five Master Teacher 1 (56%) and five Teacher III (11%) respondents representing the select public secondary schools in the Division of Cagayan de Oro City and Misamis Oriental Division. There were 10 Master Teacher and 10 Teacher I-III respondents representing. The answers were recorded and tallied.

ETCOR

INTERNATIONAL
MULTIDISCIPLINARY
RESEARCH CONFERENCE

Educational Research Center Inc.
SEC Reg. No. 2024020137294-00

Sta. Ana, Pampanga, Philippines

Website: <https://etcor.org>

iJOINED ETCOR
P - ISSN 2984-7567
E - ISSN 2945-3577

The Exigency
P - ISSN 2984-7842
E - ISSN 1908-3181

Table 6. Summary of the Responses of In-depth Interview with Teachers

Guide Questions	Responses	
	Teacher	Master Teacher
1. Do you feel compensated with your present work? a. Yes b. No	44% answered Yes, that they are comfortable with their present work and 56% answered No, they are not compensated because they have so many designations and should be given to higher position instead of them	99% confirmed that they are compensated with their present work.
2. Do you love your Job at present? What are your plans as a teacher five years from now?	60% answered that their plan five years from now is to be promoted. 37% plan to pursue graduate studies and 3% answered they will retire from the service	100 % love the job at present and plan to retire and live on the farm.
3. What is your motivation to do your Job?	46% of the teachers answered family as their motivation to do the job. 30% answered students were their motivation to do the job 9% answered salary and 5% colleagues	100% answered family as their motivation to do the job.
4. What is your perception of teacher's training/ seminars attended and performance?	48% answered it helps improve teaching and learning 40% for growth and professional development 10% it helps for self and career enhancement	100% answered it helps for growth and development of teachers.
5. What is your motivation within your workplace?	46% answered students. The love of seeing them learning and being part of their achievement. 31% answered that colleagues, with good relationships and collaboration, feel happy inside the workplace when they see the support and harmonious relationship with them. 20% answered that they love to share their skills, love the workplace and the support of the school head for doing the job.	90% of the Master teachers answered they are motivated with the learners and being happy seeing them learning. 10% answered that they are motivated with colleagues, with good relationships and collaboration, they feel happy inside the workplace and they see the support and harmonious relationship with them.

Table 6 depicts the summary of the response to an in-depth interview with teachers. The summary of the response shows that the teachers, regardless of their teaching position, confirmed that they are comfortable in their respective schools considering the dimensions of the school environment, interpersonal relationships, leadership, career management, fringe benefits, and school facilities. Overall, the teachers expressed satisfaction with the overall school environment and support they receive from colleagues and administrators. They also highlighted the importance of continuous professional development opportunities in their career growth and fulfillment.

A majority of teachers surveyed reported satisfaction with their compensation packages, citing competitive salaries as a key factor in their overall contentment. While most master teachers expressed similar satisfaction with their compensation and overall comfort with their assigned schools, one teacher noted a significant challenge: the

ETCOR

INTERNATIONAL
MULTIDISCIPLINARY
RESEARCH CONFERENCE

Educational Research Center Inc.
SEC Reg. No. 2024020137294-00

Sta. Ana, Pampanga, Philippines

Website: <https://etcor.org>

iJOINED ETCOR
P - ISSN 2984-7567
E - ISSN 2945-3577

The Exigency
P - ISSN 2984-7842
E - ISSN 1908-3181

school's distance from her residence, resulting in a lengthy commute. Nearly all teachers affirmed their comfort in their respective schools, highlighting the positive impact of fringe benefits outlined in DepEd Order No. 79, s. 2012, particularly the implementation of Step Increment for teachers specializing in science and/or mathematics. This serves as a clear example of the advantageous perks they experience within their profession.

Teachers, while generally satisfied with their current compensation and job security, expressed a desire for salary increases driven by both family responsibilities and personal aspirations for growth. This desire is reflected in their career goals: a majority aspire to promotion within the next five years, while a significant number plan to pursue graduate studies to enhance their qualifications and career prospects. Meanwhile, master teachers, having achieved significant professional milestones, prioritize a balance between professional fulfillment and personal well-being, leading them to consider retirement and pursuing personal interests. This highlights the evolving needs and priorities of teachers throughout their careers, demonstrating a desire for both financial stability and personal fulfillment.

Teachers are primarily motivated by their families and students, demonstrating a strong sense of commitment to both personal and professional responsibilities. While salary and colleagues also play a role, the primary focus remains on the impact of their work. This dedication is reflected in their job satisfaction, which stems from factors such as improving teaching and learning, pursuing professional growth and development, and enhancing their own careers. Teachers find deep fulfillment in witnessing students' learning and achievements, highlighting their passion for education. A supportive and collaborative work environment, fostered by positive relationships with colleagues, contributes significantly to their overall job satisfaction. Furthermore, opportunities to share their skills, a conducive workplace environment, and strong support from school leadership further enhance their sense of fulfillment and commitment to their roles.

Conclusions

The teachers demonstrated a link between their job satisfaction and their performance, which showed the specific components that demonstrate teaching competence observed at all times. The level of job satisfaction was also determined and observed most of the time. Also, teacher performance through their IPCRF showed a very satisfactory level. Through variation of testing, the significant relationship was found between teaching competence on critical thinking/problem-solving, teamwork/collaboration, professionalism/work ethics, and career management. Teachers' competences demonstrate high correlation value towards teachers' work competencies, which are highly correlated with the teachers job satisfaction and performance. Given the favorable outcomes of the comprehensive interview, it can be concluded that educators are making every effort to enhance their work performance competence. In the end, this helps the kids since qualified instructors can impart high-quality education effectively. Additionally, the positive correlation between job satisfaction and teaching competence indicates that happy teachers are more likely to excel in their roles, ultimately benefiting their students.

Recommendations

This research suggests a clear path forward for improving teacher development and satisfaction. By implementing targeted interventions, the school can empower teachers to excel in their roles. This includes fostering leadership skills through training and mentorship, strengthening interpersonal relationships through workshops and collaborative activities, and providing ongoing support for curriculum development and planning. Furthermore, leveraging the data from this study to inform career development programs, team-building initiatives, and promotion processes will create a more supportive and rewarding environment for teachers, ultimately leading to improved student outcomes.

REFERENCES

Arevalo, M. J., & Comighud, S. (2020). Motivation in Relation to Teachers' performance. *International Journal of Scientific Research Publications*, 10 (4): 641-653 DOI: 10.29322/IJSRP.10.04. 2020.p10071

ETCOR Educational Research Center Inc.
SEC Reg. No. 2024020137294-00

Sta. Ana, Pampanga, Philippines

Website: <https://etcor.org>

INTERNATIONAL
MULTIDISCIPLINARY
RESEARCH CONFERENCE

iJOINED ETCOR
P - ISSN 2984-7567
E - ISSN 2945-3577

The Exigency
P - ISSN 2984-7842
E - ISSN 1908-3181

- Baluyos, G. R., Rivera, H. L., & Baluyos, E. L. (2019). Teachers' Job Satisfaction and Work Performance. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 07(08), 206–221. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jss.2019.78015>
- Banerjee, N., Stearns, E., Moller, S., & Mickelson, R. A. (2017). Teacher Job Satisfaction and Student Achievement: The Roles of Teacher Professional Community and Teacher Collaboration in Schools. *American Journal of Education*, 123(2), 203–241. <https://doi.org/10.1086/689932>
- Dagoc, L. N. (2021). Job Satisfaction and Teacher Competence of Public Elementary School in Tagoloan District.
- Demir, S. (2020). The Role of Self Efficacy in Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment, Motivation and Job Involvement.
- DepEd Order No. 2, s. 2015 - Guidelines on the Establishment and Implementation of the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) in the Department of Education
- DepEd Order No. 77, s. 1991 - Personnel Economic Relief Allowance (PERA)
- DepEd Order No. 011, s. 2020 - Revised Guidelines on Alternative Work Arrangements in the Department of Education During the Period of State of National Emergency Due to COVID-19 Pandemic
- DepEd Order No. 3, s. 2016 – Hiring Guidelines for Senior High School (SHS) Teaching Positions
- DepEd Order No. 66, s. 2007 - Revised Guidelines on the Appointment and promotions of Other Teaching, Related Teaching and Non-Teaching Positions.
- DepEd Order No. 79, s. 2012 - Implementing Guidelines on the Grant of Step Increment for Teachers with Specialization in Science and/or Mathematics
- DepEd Order No. 36, s. 2013 - Department of Education Vision, Mission and Core Values (DepEd)
- DepEd Order 42, s. 2017 – National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers
- DepEd Order No. 008, s. 2019 - Revised Implementing Guidelines on the Direct Release, Use, Monitoring and Reporting of Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses Allocation of Schools, Including Other Funds Managed by Schools
- DepEd Order 66, s. 2007 – revised Guidelines on the Appointment and promotion of Other Teaching Related and Non-Teaching Positions
- Gusman, F. S. (2017). Students Competence in Technical Vocational and Livelihood Track. Grad THE 0839, G982
- Javillonar, M. G., & Boni, G. J. (2023). The Senior High School teachers' philosophical orientation and its relationship with their teaching performance. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Publications (IJMRAP)*, 5(7), 103-108, 2023.
- Kadtong, M. L., Unos, M., Antok, T. D., & Midzid, M. A. E. (2017). Teaching Performance and Job Satisfaction Among Teachers at Region XII (June 3, 2017). *Proceedings Journal of Education, Psychology and Social Science Research*, Volume 4, Issue 1, 2017, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3169846> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3169846>
- Konig, J., Jager-Biela, D. J., & Glutsch, N. (2020). Adapting to online teaching during COVID-19 school closure: teacher

ETCOR Educational Research Center Inc.
SEC Reg. No. 2024020137294-00

INTERNATIONAL
MULTIDISCIPLINARY
RESEARCH CONFERENCE

Sta. Ana, Pampanga, Philippines

Website: <https://etcor.org>

iJOINED ETCOR
P - ISSN 2984-7567
E - ISSN 2945-3577

The Exigency
P - ISSN 2984-7842
E - ISSN 1908-3181

education and teacher competence effects among early career teachers in Germany. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 43(4), 608–622. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02619768.2020.1809650>

- Kim, H. J. (2019). Exploring Pre-Service teacher's beliefs about English teaching competence, perceived competence, and actual competence. *Journal of Pan-Pacific Association of Applied Linguistics*, v23,2 p1-19.
- Maalouf, G. Y. (2021). Effects of Collaborative Leadership on Organizational Performance. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development*, 6(1), 138-144
- Mulyani, H., Meirawan, D., & Rahmadani, A. (2020). Increasing School Effectiveness Through Principals' Leadership and Teachers' Teaching Performance, Is It Possible? *Jurnal Cakrawala Pendidikan*, 39(2), 279–292. <https://doi.org/10.21831/cp.v39i2.28864>
- Olsen, A. A., & Huang, F. L. (2019). Teacher job satisfaction by principal support and teacher cooperation: Results from the schools and staffing survey. *Education Policy Analysis Archives*, 27(11). <https://doi.org/10.14507/epaa.27.4174>
- Paiton, E. C. (2017). An Evacuation of Teacher's Result-Based Performance Management Plan. Grad THE 0829, P149
- Rodriguez, N. P. (2021). School Climate on Teachers Competence and Learners Academic Achievement: Basis for Instructional and Management Plan. Grad Dis 0827 P 138 2021
- Taryana, T., Riniati, W., Haddar, G., Sembiring, D., & Mutmainnah, M. (2023). The Influence of Teacher Certification and Teaching Motivation on Teacher Performance. *Journal on Education*, 5(3), 6726-6735. <https://doi.org/10.31004/joe.v5i3.1455>
- Sides, J. D., & Cuevas, J. A. (2020). Effect of Goal Setting for Motivation, Self-Efficacy, and Performance in Elementary Mathematics. *International Journal of Instruction*, 13(4), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.29333/iji.2020.1341a>.